

1 **Reactivation of CIDE factors for anti-tumor defense.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 Inhibition of an up-regulated target is commonly understood but activation of silenced genes is not yet
8 been widely pursued as a therapeutic targeting strategy. We describe here re-activation of factors
9 functioning in induction of programmed cell death, CIDE factors *CIDEA*, *CIDEB* and *CIDEC* in CNS
10 metastasis in humans with breast cancer. Activation of cell death molecules with potent effector function
11 was likely in response to tumorigenic activity in an organ system containing both heightened sensitivity to
12 transformation as well as organ system-specific immunologic privilege. The data informed an approach by
13 which CIDE family effector activation could be selectively engineered for therapeutic targeting by
14 identification of a CIDE regulating molecule that itself could be inhibited to relieve CIDE repression. We
15 conducted transcriptome level discovery of CIDEA reactivating factors here.